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Antonio J Gómez-Núñez, Antonio Perianes-Rodríguez, Erika Sela, Joaquín Guinea, International research collaboration in personalized medicine between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean, Research Evaluation, Volume 33, 2024, rvae046, <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvae046>

is available online at:

<https://academic.oup.com/rev/article/doi/10.1093/reseval/rvae046/7863402>

International research collaboration in personalised medicine between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean

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Abstract

An analysis of research collaboration in personalised medicine between European and Latin American and Caribbean countries has been conducted in order to identify significant aspects allowing such collaboration. It aims to comprehend strategic issues for establishing research collaborations in personalised medicine between the two regions, as well as the structural factors that facilitate the collaboration.

An exhaustive literature review of the subject was the basis for the development of a framework covering several factors that are significant at different stages of the collaboration process. The framework assisted in developing a questionnaire and defining relevant questions for a final survey, which was sent to more than 1,800 corresponding authors of publications resulting from collaborations between European and Latin American and Caribbean researchers.

The results point out interesting issues like the profile of the collaboration partners, types of research collaboration, factors and motivations favouring the participation in collaborative research, ways to contact partners, funding sources and tools, main outputs or principal barriers to collaboration.

Due to the lack of available information on research collaborations in the field of personalised medicine, this type of analysis is valuable to support science and research policy-making and to evaluate the various actions, initiatives and projects carried out in this scenario. Although our methodology and analysis focused on the field of personalised medicine, the results obtained could be helpful to better understand the reality of international scientific collaborations and support the design of collaborative funding programmes in other fields.

1. Approaching personalised medicine

The term “personalised medicine” (PerMed) refers to a new approach to the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of diseases based on the analysis of certain aspects of the patient, such as genetics, environment, circumstances and lifestyle. This new practice has gained particular relevance and interest in recent years, and its growth and expansion seem inevitable. To a large extent, its acceptance and implementation have been favoured by the incessant advance of technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, deep learning, data science and big data, which have broadened the spectrum of possibilities and have boosted the development of new treatments and procedures that are better targeted and more effective when it comes to tackling the patients’ health problems. (Fröhlich et al., 2018; Hulsen et al., 2019; MacEachern & Forkert, 2021; Papadakis et al., 2019; Schork, 2019).

However, “personalised medicine” is an ambiguous and complex term that needs to be narrowly defined and delimited to facilitate its understanding and correct use. PerMed can be generally defined as “an evolving field, which allows treating patients by providing them a specific therapy according to their individual demographic, genomic or biological characteristics” (Superchi et al., 2022, p. 1). In the same vein, *The European Council Conclusion on Personalised Medicine for Patients (2015/C 421/03)* includes the following definition:

Personalised medicine refers to a medical model using characterisation of individuals’ phenotypes and genotypes (e.g., molecular profiling, medical imaging, lifestyle data) for tailoring the right therapeutic strategy for the right person at the right time, and/or to determine the predisposition to disease and/or to deliver timely and targeted prevention. Personalised medicine relates to the broader concept of patient-centred care, which takes into account that, in general, healthcare systems need to better respond to patient needs. (Council of the European Union, 2015, p. 3)

It is important to bear in mind that the terms “personalised medicine” and “precision medicine” have sometimes been used interchangeably as synonyms. However, as some authors point out, both terms have particularities that make them distinct. Ho and colleagues (2020) argue that personalised medicine shares with precision medicine the fact that it considers the patient as an individual from diagnosis to treatment, but unlike precision medicine it does not inherently rely on large datasets or population-based approaches to redefine disease. Hurtado (2022) refers to the concern of the US National Research Council of the National Academies (NRC) about the erroneous approach of believing that personalised medicine provides treatments and prevention that are unique to each individual. In this regard, Sarvan and Prasanthi Nori (2021) have this to say:

Precision medicine, therefore, does not mean to develop a drug for a single patient, but rather a subset of patients with a disease redefined by a more precise taxonomy. The term is defined less specifically for PM. Many consider it synonymous with precision medicine, but it is also possible to use PM to connote treatment of individual patients, rather than groups. Individual patient PM depends on many contextual factors that are independent of the underlying disease as defined by the precision medicine. These factors may include custom dosing,

concomitant therapies, therapy response, drug metabolism and preferences of patients.

In this respect, the approach used in this article is to consider the terms “personalised medicine” and “precision medicine” as synonyms, although, in line with the European Commission, we have chosen to use “personalised medicine” as the prevailing term. This decision stems from the simple and logical reasoning that it is preferable to act in line with the strategy implemented by the European Union, where research in personalised medicine is a priority issue aimed at strengthening and optimising the health care of European citizens. This approach is also sensible in view of the fact that this work began under the EU-LAC PerMed project (2019), aimed at promoting cooperation in personalised medicine between Europe (EU) and Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC).

2. PerMed collaboration initiatives

The importance and great acceptance that personalised medicine has acquired in recent years is evident, for example, in the number of initiatives and/or projects involving PerMed. Some especially noteworthy actions have been run with European Commission financing, confirming that today personalised medicine has become a real priority within the framework of European Union research. As an example, within the Horizon 2020 programme, we can find cases such as ERA PerMed and ICPeMed. The European Research Area Network for Personalised Medicine (ERA PerMed) (2017), which is a specific ERA-Net Cofund in personalised medicine, aims to create joint calls for proposals to launch collaborative research projects in personalised medicine through the national funding agencies of a network of European and non-European countries. The aim is to maximise effort, align national research strategies, promote excellence, strengthen the competitiveness of European actors in the field of personalised medicine and enhance European collaboration with third countries. Meanwhile, the International Consortium for Personalised Medicine (ICPeMed) (2016) is a platform to share ideas and support communication, research, funding and implementation of projects and/or initiatives in personalised medicine. Its main objective is to try to align research and funding for such initiatives at both the European and the international level. To achieve this, it also proposes the design of a common framework that includes the main requirements for promoting the implementation and development of PerMed initiatives, including infrastructure, resources and the necessary regulatory standards and procedures. Furthermore, ICPeMed works in close collaboration with ERA PerMed in a range of coordination and support actions (CSAs) funded by the European Commission, as well as in other associated and related initiatives on the subject. This has given rise to what is known as the ICPeMed Family, which involves a major commitment to PerMed research and implementation at both the European and the transnational level. It covers initiatives of great value, such as:

- Interregional Coordination for a Fast and Deep Uptake of Personalised Health ([Regions4PerMed](#)).
- Securing the Adoption of Personalised Health in Regions ([SAPHIRE](#)).
- Health Economic Models for Personalised Medicine ([HEcoPerMed](#)).

- Widening EU-LAC Policy and Research Cooperation in Personalised Medicine ([EU-LAC PerMed](#)).
- Cooperation Between China and Europe in Personalised Medicine ([SINO-EU PerMed](#)).
- Integrating China in the International Consortium for Personalised Medicine ([IC2PerMed](#)).
- Personalised Medicine Trials ([PERMIT](#)).
- Building Links Between Europe and Africa in Personalised Medicine ([EU-Africa PerMed](#)).
- A Personalized Prevention roadmap for the future HEalThcare ([PROPHET](#)).

In today's increasingly global competitive world, it is virtually impossible for any single country to avoid research collaboration with other countries, because science, technology and innovation have increasingly become a global and collaborative undertaking (Chen et al., 2019). As the results of ICPeMed and ERA PerMed have shown, international collaboration in PerMed is essential to achieve a critical mass of data from diverse sources to develop and train algorithms and models used in PM approaches, so that these are not limited to a specific regional context, thus expanding and converting the usefulness of their results for the common good (ICPeMed & ERA PerMed, s. f.).

3. Related research

Numerous scholarly papers have addressed different facets of research collaboration and have examined research collaboration in various contexts. As a result, there is no generally accepted standard definition of the term "research collaboration". Furthermore, the definition of the term is frequently and simply based on understanding what collaboration is and what its implications are (Bukvova, 2010). Jassawalla and Sashittal (1998, p. 239) define collaboration as "the coming together of diverse interests and people to achieve a common purpose via interactions, information sharing, and coordination of activities". Laudel (2002, p. 5) puts the focus on research collaboration, which she defines as a "system of research activities by several actors related in a functional way and coordinated to attain a research goal corresponding with these actors' research goals or interests".

From a bibliometric perspective, it is common to understand collaboration as the result of research activity embodied in the form of publications generated by different actors (co-authorship). But research collaboration can be treated from other points of view, for example, through the analysis of participation in research projects, the generation of research infrastructure, the design and development of experiments and pilot tests and the creation and launch of new products and/or services. Then, as Kwiek (2018) points out, research collaboration does not necessarily lead to scientific publications. However, because of the difficulties involved in studying research collaboration using alternative approaches to bibliometrics, studies based on the analysis of publication co-authorship have become the widely accepted norm. Kwiek refers to the different ways of approaching collaboration, mainly by examining the activity done jointly by actors in different systems (between) or by actors in the same system (within). Furthermore,

Kwiek's levels of collaboration match those proposed in previous studies by authors such as Katz and Martin (1997, p. 10), who classify forms of collaboration according to various levels, including individuals, groups, departments, institutions, sectors and countries, taking account also of the internal (intra) or external (inter) nature of the collaboration. For Katz and Martin, "international collaboration means collaboration between nations while intra-national collaboration means collaboration within a single nation" (p. 10). Leydesdorff and Wagner (2008) suggest that "international collaboration in science can be considered as a communications network that is different from national systems and has its own internal dynamics".

3.1. Benefits of collaboration

There is evidence that collaboration ensures that scientists and researchers improve the quality, impact and visibility of their work. Thus, the benefits generated by research collaboration seem to be reason enough for collaboration to become a key element of research policies at national and supranational levels alike (Abramo et al., 2009). Therefore, approaches based on the analysis of collaboration at the supranational level, for example, between geographical areas (e.g., the Maghreb, North America) or political and/or economic alliances of countries (e.g., the EU, CELAC), are also an object of study and interest, especially for policy and decision makers. Good examples of this can be found in work on research collaboration in all kinds of fields of knowledge: agriculture (Roseboom, 2019), biodiversity and climate change (Dangles et al., 2016), education (Woldegiyorgis et al., 2022), medicine and health (González-Alcaide et al., 2020; Horby et al., 2015), etc.

Numerous studies have clearly outlined the main advantages or benefits of carrying out research projects and activities in a collaborative way, and there exists a general consensus on this topic. Achury-Saldaña et al. (2022) point to "greater visibility, better research financing and enhanced social impact of the results" as the main benefits of research collaboration, understood as the co-authorship of publications. Similarly, Kwiek (2018) claims that "multiple-institution papers are more highly cited than single-institution papers, and papers with international coauthors are more highly cited than papers with domestic co-authors". Based on this and similar research, it seems clear that there are reasons for researchers and academics to collaborate, at the very least, by co-authoring scholarly publications. Bukvova (2010) summarises some of the positive effects collaboration has for researchers, including access to knowledge and resources and the possibility of pooling them to address complex issues, the exchange of ideas across disciplines, the learning of new skills and an increase in productivity and in the quality of research results.

International collaboration has particular advantages. The book entitled *Examining Core Elements of International Research Collaboration: Summary of a Workshop* (National Academy of Sciences et al., 2011), lists concrete benefits of international collaboration in science and technology, including: (1) door opening even when political and economic relations between some countries are complex; (2) problem solving, since many global challenges need science and technology approaches to solve them, and international collaboration facilitates researchers' access to information, ideas and resources, thus accelerating the development of new knowledge and innovation for this purpose; (3)

lasting relationships, especially thanks to the invaluable help of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and the open innovation model currently in place, enabling scientists and researchers to collaborate with peers around the world; (4) democratic values, since research findings derived from science and technology cooperation are “based on open and fluid discussion, and conclusions are based on fact, not on issues of national origin, age, ethnicity, gender, or political views”.

3.2. Reasons for collaboration

The main reasons or factors that motivate researchers and their organisations to collaborate at different levels are also a frequent topic of study. Based on a review of previous work, Katz & Martin (1997) offer a compilation of a number of such factors. One is researchers’ desire to increase their own scientific popularity, visibility and recognition. Another is progressive growth in the specialisation of science and knowledge and the advancement of scientific disciplines, which not only means that a researcher needs more and more knowledge to make significant advances, but also encourages developments such as cross-fertilisation between disciplines, i.e. interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary collaboration. Lee and Bozeman (2005) report that collaborating with prestigious research groups affords greater ease in obtaining public funding as well as higher productivity and more possibilities of gaining greater recognition and visibility. Along similar lines, Abramo et al. (2009) cite the increasing specialisation of science, the complexity of the problems being investigated and the high costs of the equipment needed to carry out research as the main factors favouring the increase in research collaboration.

Bukvova (2010) focuses mainly on two groups of factors, which he calls internal and external. The first group, internal factors, includes leadership, reputation, equality and prestige. In the group of external factors, we find access to funding and resources, the organisation's own culture and institutional support. Moradi et al. (2020) use qualitative techniques to study international collaboration in the health area and conclude that research collaboration is influenced by *personal factors* (being competent to communicate in English, participating in scientific events and associations, joining the editorial boards of international journals, etc.), *organisational factors* (providing sabbaticals or visiting fellows, fostering institutions’ international ranking, etc.) and *government factors* (considering the background and good practices of successful countries and improving relationships with them). Qualitative techniques are also used by Maluleka et al. (2016) to identify factors influencing research collaboration, although their research focuses on schools of library and information science in South Africa. Based on information obtained from surveys, Maluleka et al. identify eight essential factors: networking, sharing resources, enhancing productivity, educating students, overcoming intellectual isolation, accomplishing projects in a limited time, learning from peers and receiving incentives (e.g., in financial form).

3.3. Research collaboration between Europe and Latin America

International research collaboration between Europe and Latin America is not an unusual phenomenon, and proof of this are the numerous and generous efforts and initiatives launched by the European Union to strengthen joint work and improve results. It is common to find research papers that address collaboration between Europe and Latin America from a bibliometric perspective, i.e., based on analysis of the scientific literature,

such as Pineda et al. (2020) and Belli and Baltá (2019). Spain appears as one of Latin America's regular collaborators, as can be seen in studies such as De Filippo et al. (2008), where scientific production in different knowledge areas and network development are addressed through the co-authorship of scientific publications by the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) in collaboration with Latin-American institutions. Collaborations between Spain and Latin-American countries have been addressed by many other investigators as well, especially bibliometric researchers, such as De Filippo et al. (2010), Molina et al. (2010), Alonso Arroyo (2016) and Segado-Boj et al. (2021). Gaillard and Arvanitis (2013) confirm a special emphasis on Spanish-LAC collaboration after examining co-authorship in scientific publications. They state that scientific and technological collaboration between LAC and Europe has existed since the growth of scientific advancement in both regions, although “these relationships became institutionalized at the beginning of the 20th century”. A bibliometric analysis of co-authorship included in their study shows that medicine, physics and biology are the main subject areas of collaboration between Europe and LAC.

Europe's efforts to promote research with LAC are evident. Many of these endeavours have materialised in the form of agreements, actions, instruments or initiatives in the EU's various Research Framework Programmes (some of which have already been mentioned). Collaboration between countries from the two regions through participation in European research projects has also been the subject of study in work such as that of Levin and Kreimere (2013), who examine the consortiums of the collaborative projects funded by the EU through Framework Programmes 6 and 7 (FP6 and FP7) including Latin-American groups and institutions. More recently, Feld and Kreimer (2020) have studied the involvement of Latin-American research organisations from countries including Brazil, Argentina, Mexico, Chile and Colombia in consortiums funded by the EU's 7th Framework Programme. They claim scientific connections are becoming more complex and Latin-American research groups are weaving an increasing number of international alliances.

The way Latin-American researchers participate in European projects has also been examined by Uribe-Mallarino (2022), who uses information from CORDIS and the Open Aire repository to review the involvement of a sample of LAC countries including Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia and Mexico in FP7 (2007-2013) and FP8 (also known as Horizon 2020, covering 2014-2020). Uribe-Mallarino's final goal is to discover the real role of LAC countries in collaborations under EU research and innovation projects, just to ascertain if they are working together as equals or are the focus of science diplomacy. The author concludes that as third countries, LAC countries have been moderately involved in the last two EU funding programmes, but their level of participation is gradually rising. In his own words, LAC countries' participation has been conditioned by factors like “the individual countries' STI capability, their internalization policy and science diplomacy effort, the Framework Programme rules, and the European Commission's policies for science diplomacy” (Uribe-Mallarino, 2022, p. 25).

4. Objectives

The main objective of this research paper is to identify and analyse recent PerMed research collaboration between the EU and LAC, to obtain detailed information on the significant aspects that make such collaboration possible and to make concrete recommendations for ICPeMed and for LAC and EU research-funding institutions to better promote international research and innovation collaboration in PerMed.

Three main research questions are addressed:

1. What are the most important strategic issues in setting up research collaborations between EU and LAC in PerMed?
2. What are the significant structural factors for setting up such collaborations and taking them forward?
3. What have been the main outcomes and benefits of the research collaboration?

This research stems from part of the activity done under the EU-LAC PerMed project (2019) aimed at improving the participation and integration of LAC countries in ICPeMed and ERAPerMed to expand PerMed research and innovation policies and favour PerMed implementation in health systems worldwide. This project was intended to improve the health and quality of life of patients and society in general, in accordance with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal 3, "Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages" (United Nations, 2022).

The findings of this research are also intended to demonstrate the usefulness and benefits of this type of analysis as a valuable tool for both designing and evaluating funding programmes supporting international research collaborations. More information on what drives researchers from different countries and regions to collaborate and the issues that can arise in international collaborations could support the work of officers in funding agencies, government bodies or other public organisations involved in the design of funding tools and instruments that support international science and research collaboration, as well as in ex-post evaluation of research programmes.

5. Methodology

5.1. General issues

As shown in figure 1, the methodology designed for this work comprises five work stages, namely: [1] a literature review; [2] the development of a framework; [3] the creation of a questionnaire with sample questions; [4] the release of the final online survey containing the questions selected as appropriate; and [5] the processing, analysis and presentation of the survey results.

Figure 1. Description of the methodology

5.2. Literature review

This research work started with an extensive literature review on international research collaborations in the field of biomedicine, focusing on research collaboration between EU and LAC countries. The objective was to better understand the importance of international research collaboration and, at the same time, to gain a broader understanding of the different elements and aspects of this activity. The review process covered a selection of scientific and scholarly publications from reputable sources, mainly peer-reviewed academic journals, which were retrieved from recognised international databases such as PubMed and Scopus, which have broad coverage in biomedical journals. Google Scholar and alternative sources like CORDIS and Zenodo were also used to search not only scholarly literature but also other document types, including reports, working papers and policy briefs.

Based on this review, it seems clear that international research collaboration has been the subject of considerable research efforts in recent decades, especially by the EU. This finding is also in line with the various initiatives, actions and projects discussed above in the “Introduction” and “Related Work” chapters of this paper.

5.3. Theoretical framework for assessing EU-LAC research collaboration in personalised medicine

A theoretical framework was conceived as a tool to help design the survey in the context of the EULAC-PerMed project. The preparation of the framework began with prior consultation of a number of inspirational works on research collaboration at different levels, including Borrel-Damian et al. (2014), Bukvova (2010), Dusdal and Powell (2021), Guinea et al. (2015), Hall et al. (2019), Meißner et al. (2022), Shih et al. (2020) and Tigges et al. (2019).

Based on the review of selected works and the authors' own experience, the framework was built in four main sections covering many factors that are significant at different stages of the collaboration process. These sections are:

[I] Strategic approaches in setting up research collaboration (motivations)

This section is about why researchers from LAC and the EU collaborate in research projects. It talks about the different strategies and reasons behind their involvement, including

- active involvement in cutting-edge science,
- increased research capacity,
- access to other partners' expertise,
- broadening of research funding sources and
- opportunity to provide input for public health development.

[II] Structural factors in setting up research collaborations and taking them forward

This section focuses on how LAC and European researchers work together on structural factors. It considers issues that pertain to minimising barriers and giving support in the creation and sustainability of these partnerships, namely,

- organisational and institutional support,
- funding for bi-regional/international research collaboration and
- interest in/prioritisation of research into personalised medicine.

[III] Facilitating aspects for successful research collaborations

This section encompasses a series of aspects favouring the establishment and progress of collaborative research initiatives, which generally vary as partnerships expand and move forward. They are:

- effective leadership/coordination,
- previous successful experience with the partners,
- commitment and interdependence between the partners,
- opportunities for discussion and disagreement and
- justice and fairness in the collaboration.

[IV] Goals, outcomes and benefits of research collaborations

This section compiles some of the main outcomes and benefits derived from collaborative research initiatives and projects, such as:

- knowledge production (scientific publications, etc.),
- capacity building,
- the ability to inform health policy and practice and
- socioeconomic benefits.

Figure 2 represents the theoretical framework, its four main sections, the aspects considered in each section and the relationships between sections.

Figure 2. Theoretical framework for assessing research collaborations between EU and LAC institutions in PerMed

5.4. Questionnaire design and validation

The main objective of the survey was to gain a better understanding of the research collaborations that occur between EU and LAC researchers in the PerMed field: why this activity takes place, what influences researchers to collaborate, how the collaboration is funded (if at all), the challenges collaborators face in working together and the positive outcomes.

As already mentioned, the survey's development was also based on the principles defined in our theoretical framework. The framework was extremely helpful in developing the questionnaire and defining relevant, suitable questions. Most of the questions were designed with closed answers to facilitate survey completion and reduce the time needed to answer the questions. This is an important point, since it means that in a way the answers were guided. For this reason, it proved essential to have developed a framework first and to have based the survey's preparation on previous research that also used surveys.

However, due to strategic issues of the EULAC-PerMed project, the questionnaire was developed on the basis of only three of the four dimensions represented in the framework. Table 1 lists all the dimensions and subdimensions finally used to build the questionnaire

and the subsequent survey. The questionnaire was also validated internally by the consortium members in two online workshops.

DIMENSION	SUBDIMENSION
Strategic approaches in setting up research collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Active involvement in cutting-edge science ▪ Increased research capacity ▪ Access to other partners' expertise ▪ Broadening of research funding sources ▪ Opportunity to provide input for public health development
Structural factors in setting up research collaborations and taking them forward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Organisational and institutional support ▪ Funding for bi-regional/international research collaboration ▪ Interest in/prioritisation of PerMed research
Goals, outcomes and benefits of research collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Knowledge production (scientific publications, etc.) ▪ Capacity building ▪ The ability to inform health policy and practice ▪ Socioeconomic benefits

Table 1. Dimensions and subdimensions used to develop the EULAC-PerMed survey

The final version of the questionnaire is included at the end of this paper (Annex 1).

5.5. Online survey: recipient selection criteria

In order to find potential respondents to our survey, we exhaustively searched the PubMed and Scopus databases for academic journal articles on personalised and precision medicine. To narrow our search, a 10-year time window was set between 2012 and 2021. In addition, the articles retrieved had to meet the condition of having been authored by at least one author from LAC and one from the EU (including Turkey and Israel). According to these criteria, we found 2922 jointly co-authored articles with authors from LAC and authors from the EU, Turkey or Israel. From this article set, we identified a total of 2314 corresponding authors. Of these, 831 were from LAC countries, and the remaining 1483 were from the EU, Turkey or Israel.

We sent the survey to the corresponding authors of the articles only, because we wanted to hear the opinions of experienced leading researchers from both the EU and LAC on the topics addressed in the questionnaire. Our decision was further justified by two main facts.

Firstly, most scientific and academic journals require that each article have an author identified as the corresponding author. This author is, among other things, the person mainly responsible for communicating with the journal and with readers in case of any questions related to the research article (Mattsson et al., 2011). Thus, the contact information of corresponding authors, including their email address, is available in journals and is accessible to readers.

Secondly, two details of scientific publications, namely, the correspondence address and the order in which the authors' names are listed, may indicate the co-authors' role and contribution to research. "In papers with international collaboration, studying the order of signatures and participation as corresponding authors may also provide information about dominance and leadership in research" (González-Alcaide et al., 2017).

With this in mind, we decided to contact the corresponding authors using the email addresses from our article set. We did so in the full conviction that the corresponding authors would be the most well-informed, competent people to answer our survey questions. The survey was prepared using SurveyMonkey (Momentive, 1999) and sent to the 1863 researchers (1248 from the EU and 615 from LAC) whose email addresses were available. Email notes with the link to the survey were first sent out on 7 June 2022. A reminder was sent three weeks later to researchers who had not responded.

6. Results

After the two rounds of emails, a total of 136 responses were obtained, so the response rate was 7.3%. There is a large body of literature on the appropriateness of response rates in surveys and their possible impact on results and findings. One of the main problems identified is nonresponse bias. According to Hikmet and Chen (2003), "Surveys by mail can result in very low response rate raising the possibility of non-response bias". However, authors such as Groves (2006) and more recently Hendra and Hill (2019) point to a lack of compelling evidence as well as "little relationship between survey response rates and nonresponse bias". In fact, they state that "lower response rate targets may yield results that are as valid, more timely, and less expensive". Likewise, Alreck and Settle (1985) suggest that a rate of, say, 30% in mail studies would be unusual, while response rates of 5 to 10% might be considered more common. In any case, the reliability of the data depends on the sample collected, not the number of surveys delivered. In addition, it is easy to access previous research and academic literature showing that a low survey response rate does not influence or limit the results and findings, such as Wlastrom and Wilson (1997), Hikmet and Chen (2003) and Gregory et al. (2020, 2022), who report response rates of 10.4%, 8.47%, 1.1% and 1.62%, respectively. A different matter is the survey completion rate, which was 84%, i.e., some respondents started to complete the survey but did not submit it.

In the mailing process, it was difficult to ascertain the exact number of researchers who had received the invitation to participate in the survey. We noticed that a significant number of the corresponding author email addresses we had identified (about 20% of the total set) were not operative. In line with this, a study that emailed corresponding authors in various fields of biomedicine reported that only slightly more than half of the researchers responded to the information request (Teunis et al., 2015). In our particular case, a large proportion of the message delivery failures may have been due to authors' having left their institutions or changed their e-mail address. Furthermore, it is quite likely that our invitation to participate in the survey was identified as spam. How many of our e-mail messages were sent directly to the researcher's spam folder is, however, unlikely ever to be known.

Table 2 shows the number of institutions per country of the researchers who responded to the survey, grouped by region. We also created the category of “Other” to include the particular case of a respondent working in an institution located in the United States. The majority of the responses from the group of EU countries (68 out of 136 countries) came from researchers working in Spain (19), Italy (15) and France (10), which together accounted for 65.67% of the EU countries and 32.35% of the complete list. Brazil (27), Mexico (12), Argentina (8) and Chile (8) made up the top group of LAC countries (67 out of 136 countries), accounting for 56.52% of the LAC countries and 28.68% of the full country set.

REGION	COUNTRY	INSTITUTIONS	SUBTOTAL
EU	Spain	19	68
	Italy	15	
	France	10	
	Germany	6	
	Portugal	6	
	Denmark	2	
	Belgium	1	
	Czech Republic	1	
	Hungary	1	
	Iceland	1	
	Norway	1	
	Romania	1	
	Sweden	1	
	Switzerland	1	
The Netherlands	1		
LAC	Brazil	27	67
	Mexico	12	
	Argentina	8	
	Chile	8	
	Colombia	4	
	Uruguay	4	
	Peru	3	
	Costa Rica	1	
	Ecuador	1	
OTHER	United States	1	1
	TOTAL	136	136

Table 2. Countries of the research institutions of the 136 respondents

The demographic questions included in the survey also provided further data of interest. The gender question revealed that 39.71% of the respondents were women, while the remaining 60.29% were men. When asked about their job positions, the majority of the respondents (46.32%) indicated that they were principal investigators (PIs)/group leaders. The next most-numerous group was senior group leaders (30.88% of responses). Much further behind was the “Other” category, including professors, analysts and scientists (11.03%), and the group of professionals with the lowest frequency of responses was clinicians, postdoc/research fellows, healthcare professionals and PhD students (below 5%).

Interesting data were also collected on the survey participants’ institutions. As can be seen in figure 3, 47% of the participants were attached to universities, slightly more than 24% worked at public research institutes and approximately 8% belonged to private research institutes. Almost 12% worked in hospitals, while almost 9% of the respondents worked for private companies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) or other types of organisations.

Figure 3. Type of research institution of the survey respondents

One of the first key questions related to collaborative research activity concerned the main field of research in which the surveyed researchers had worked in collaboration with other researchers from European or LAC countries. Figure 4 shows that just over 34% of respondents had collaborated in the field of cancer, which was the main field of collaboration by a wide margin. “Genomics, proteomics, genetics” and “Infectious diseases” each accounted for 11% of the total. None of the other fields reported by respondents added up to over 6% of the total, with the exception of the “Others” category (12.5% of the responses). “Others” included residual options such as allergic diseases, autoimmune diseases, endocrinology, microbiology, nutritional and metabolic care of patients with diseases, ophthalmology and visual sciences, physical activity, phytotherapy, rare and immunological disorders, severe asthma and transplants.

Figure 4. Major research fields in collaboration between researchers from EU and LAC

Of the total number of researchers surveyed, 71.65% had collaborated in the last 10 years with colleagues from the other side. The 28.35% of researchers who had not done so were asked what obstacles had prevented their participation in collaborative research activities. Several answers were possible, and respondents pointed to a number of causes. The most frequently claimed obstacles were these:

- Funding for collaborative research not available (68.18%)
- Lack of /insufficient infrastructure (20.45%)
- Lack of institutional support (20.45%)
- Difficulties in sharing data/samples (13.64%)
- Funding timelines inadequate to conduct research (11.36%)
- Insufficient time to collaborate in international projects (9.09%)
- Other (11.36%), where various reasons were given, such as different research priorities, certain reluctance or suspicion that the EU does not consider LAC researchers at the same level and lack of opportunities to find collaborators.

Despite the potential obstacles to collaboration, almost 50% of the researchers surveyed working in biomedical and PerMed research felt it was “extremely important” for their success as a researcher to collaborate with colleagues from the EU and/or LAC. However, only 6.98% of the researchers surveyed stated that more than 75% of the research they conducted was done in collaboration with Europe/LAC institutions, while 17.44% stated that 50-75% of their work was a collaborative effort with Europe/LAC institutions, and 29.07% indicated that their percentage of collaborative work was 25-50%. The largest researcher group, 46.51% of the respondents, reported that less than 25% of their total work was collaborative.

The main types of partners for collaboration are shown in figure 5. “Scientists from other institutes/organisations” (88.37%) are the most common type of partner, followed by “Hospitals/healthcare professionals” (44.19%) and, far behind, “Research

infrastructures” (12.79%) and “Consortium of private, public and scientific partners” (10.47%). Collaborations with different types of companies, NGOs, public bodies and others show lower rates. Here, as in several survey questions, the sum of the percentages of the different options is greater than 100, because this was posed as a multiple-choice question.

Figure 5. Main types of collaboration partners

Figure 6 shows that international research projects (66.28%) were the most common type of research collaboration action. Nevertheless, “Capacity-building activities” (53.49%), “Non-formal collaboration” (52.33%) and “Networking activities” (45.35%) were also very prominent.

Figure 6. Types of research collaboration conducted in the last 10 years

Figure 7 shows the main phases of the translational research continuum in which collaboration between EU and LAC researchers participating in the survey happened. “Basic research” (60.47%) was reported as the most frequent research phase, followed by “Applied biomedical research” (45.35%). Further down the scale, “Translations to humans”, “Translations to patients” and “Translations to practice” presented identical values, with 20.93% of the responses. The last two positions were occupied by “Translation to community” (9.3%) and “Other” (3.49%), where respondents had the possibility to provide other options that did not fit into the phases indicated in the survey.

Figure 7. Phases of the translational research continuum

The survey included some questions related to structural factors, where researchers reported the key elements that have encouraged and made it possible for them to establish collaborative research partnerships between the EU and LAC. These factors, which play a significant role in the success and significance of collaborations, are shown in figure 8 below. The factor overwhelmingly considered most significant by the researchers is “Knowledge of collaborator’s work/their knowledge of my work”. After this, “Previously worked with the collaborator” is also considered very significant, although to a lesser degree. Other factors, such as “Introduced through another researcher”, “Met at a conference/event” and “Facilitated by institution/funder/network” are judged significant in around 50% of the responses.

Figure 8. Main factors in favour of participation in collaborative research

The most common ways of establishing contact with other researchers are reflected in figure 9. The first option listed refers to intentional forms of contact, using means such as letters, emails or phone calls (51.25%). Interestingly, and not far behind, the second most-selected form of contact involves informal or chance-based methods, for example, participation in or attendance at scientific events and meetings such as workshops, conferences and presentations, as well as visits to other institutions to acquire new skills or knowledge (47.50%). In third place, and at a considerable distance from the other options, are contacts by recommendation or referral by trusted colleagues.

Figure 9. Main ways to establish contact with partner teams

Finding out what encourages researchers to collaborate is fundamental to gaining a better understanding of the collaboration process. This information can be especially important for scientific policy makers, to help them design collaborative research actions and strategies that are interesting and attractive to researchers. Figure 10 shows the main motivations expressed by the surveyed researchers and the degree of relevance for a set of pre-defined statements. As can be seen, the three main motivations that moved the researchers participating in our survey to collaborate were "To access expertise, interdisciplinarity and cross-fertilisation of ideas" (for 70% of the responses, a "very relevant" motivation) followed by "To build or maintain links with researchers overseas" (with just over 63% of the responses) and "To address an international research question" (with 60% of the responses). The motivations considered least relevant were "To find a research job out of your country" ("not relevant at all" for 62.50% of the responses and "To collaborate with a business based overseas" ("irrelevant" for 55.00% of the responses).

Figure 10. Main motivations for participating in collaborative research

Apart from the personal motivations mentioned above, another important reason for researchers to collaborate is the possibility of obtaining some kind of funding to support research activity. Funding also helps researchers attract and recruit new talent through research grants and contracts, improve infrastructure and access to technical equipment (medical and laboratory instruments, hardware, software, etc.) and share and disseminate knowledge and research results through scientific events (workshops, congresses, etc.) and publications (open access articles, specialised blogs, etc.).

The surveyed researchers were also asked about access to funding sources that have played an important role in establishing collaborations with European or LAC countries (figure 11). Seventy percent of the responses were that the most important source was “Direct home public funding both at national or regional levels”. Less popular but no less interesting are other options, such as “Home institution funding” and “EU research funding (ERC, H2020, HorizonEurope, other)”, with 38.75% and 32.50%, respectively.

Figure 11. Funding sources that play a significant role in supporting collaborations with Europe/LAC

The survey also sought to identify the types of funding tools that have supported or facilitated researchers in their quest to conduct collaborative research activities (figure 12). From researchers' point of view, three tools were especially significant for this purpose. The top tool, with more than 90% of the responses, was project-based funding options, mainly grants. In second place, with slightly above 41% of the responses, was institutional funding (including, for instance, block funding, competitive funding and cooperation agreements with universities). The third financing tool for collaborations, named by 40% of the researchers, was mobility programmes.

Figure 12. Types of funding tools that support collaboration

A specific question in the survey verified that in most cases the funding that was received to help carry out collaborative research with EU/LAC countries focused on general biomedical/health research topics. Funding that particularly targeted PerMed accounted for only 5% of the cases. On the other hand, in 23.75% of the cases, the funding was intended to address collaborative research activities concerning both general biomedical/health and PerMed or about another topic entirely.

One of the aspects of collaborative research that arouses the most interest, especially in fields such as scientific policy and science and research evaluation, is research outcomes. Outcomes are usually considered not only as evidence of the research activity done, but also as a way of giving back to society, since much of the research done in advanced societies takes place in public organisations and is supported by public funds. The survey also included a specific set of questions addressing issues related to the outcomes and benefits of collaborative research. Figure 13 shows the main outputs of collaborative activity according to the participating researchers' own experience. By and large, the researchers selected four major options. Almost all (91.25%) agreed on "Jointly authored publications" as the first output of collaborative research. Three other output types also received a high number of responses, at similar percentage rates. They were "Grants awarded in collaboration with partner institutes" (62.50%), "Undergraduate, PhD, master's degree" (57.50%) and "Conference presentations in collaboration with partner institutes" (56.25%).

Figure 13. Main types of research collaboration output

Despite the numerous benefits presented above, researchers also identified a series of barriers that limit or prevent research in collaboration with partners. Fifty-five percent of the researchers who participated in the study pointed to a “Lack of specific funding opportunities for joint actions” as the main barrier to collaborating at an international level. At a considerable distance, with percentages that ranged between 21% and almost 29%, were other options, such as “Funding timelines inadequate to conduct research”, “Academic standards: disparities in competitiveness, intensity of work and general academic environments”, “Lack of institutional support or even opposition to participation in international collaborations by researchers or institutions” and “Insufficient time to collaborate in international projects”. All the barriers initially identified and the response percentages are shown in figure 14 below.

Figure 14. Main barriers that limit or prevent research collaborations with EU/LAC researchers

However, despite the reported barriers, when the researchers were asked whether they had collaborated with other regions in health/personalised medicine research, only 26.25% said they never had. The remaining 73.75%, therefore, had had some research experience in collaboration with other regions. Figure 15 shows the other main regions with which researchers had collaborated. North America was the leader, with just over 83%, followed far behind by the rest of the available options.

Figure 15. Main regions with which the researchers had also partnered in collaboration

Just over 62% of the researchers described the ease of collaborating with other regions as the same as the ease of collaborating with the EU/LAC. On the other hand, for just over 18% of researchers, collaborating with other regions was easier, while for a similar percentage of researchers, collaborative activity with regions other than the EU/LAC was more difficult.

7. Discussion and conclusions

This research provides specific information of considerable interest about research collaboration in the field of PerMed between EU and LAC countries. In addition to information from the review of the literature on the subject, this study provides additional first-hand information from a survey of the main actors involved in collaborative research activities on PerMed, EU and LAC researchers themselves. Little prior information is available on research collaborations concerning PerMed (and many other topics). Further work such as this is not only advisable, but necessary, especially as a supporting tool for scientific policy-making, science evaluation and assessment of the various actions carried out in this context (e.g., research proposal selection and funding, evaluation of specific research projects and entire programmes, implementation of new research strategies and the termination of others).

However, it is important to remember that the survey was sent only to corresponding authors of scientific publications, most of whom work for public research institutions; this is an important limitation of this study. In any case, as most of the survey participants were senior researchers with long experience in collaborating with researchers from other regions, we consider that the information they provided in the survey is valuable and meaningful for our purposes.

Furthermore, the survey responses have given us a better understanding and clearer and deeper insight into the two issues raised in our research questions as well as some

additional aspects in connection with research collaboration between the two regions. On the question of the *strategic issues* behind collaboration, almost half of the researchers said they believed collaborative work with researchers from institutions in Europe or LAC in the field of biomedical research and PerMed is a guarantee of success for their professional careers.

The collaborations reported by the participants took place mainly between researchers from universities and other public research organisations. Few collaborations were set up with other types of institutions (government agencies, NGOs), and even fewer with companies. These findings agree with previous studies that point to a series of factors that hinder collaboration and knowledge exchange between universities and companies, such as universities' usual long-term orientation, intellectual property issues and administrative procedures (Bruneel et al., 2010). The limited collaboration with companies could also be the reason why the main phases of the translational research continuum reported by the researchers were basic and applied biomedical research: subsequent phases may require special facilities or equipment usually available in large or leading companies only, not at universities or public research centres (Note that just over 83% of the survey participants worked for universities, public research organisations and hospitals, while only 11.03% worked for private companies or private research institutes).

Given our own professional experience and background, we were unsurprised that the main forms of collaboration reported by the respondents were international research projects, training actions (such as stays in foreign research centres), collaborative work to prepare scientific publications and networking activities. In many cases, these forms of collaboration can be considered non-optional, since they are essential requirements for career advancement and stabilisation in the research field. Any researcher seeking professional success must gather publications (“publish or perish”), demonstrate leadership (by participating in and directing research projects), network (by giving speeches and presentations at congresses, workshops, etc.) and build capacity (by participating in training courses, mobility and international stays, etc.) at the international level.

With regard to the *structural factors* of collaboration, respondents said that the most relevant or highly relevant factors encouraging them to participate in collaborative research activities with Europe or LAC countries (and facilitating the actual performance of the activity) were factors involving some kind of prior knowledge or contact, relationship or interaction with peers. This might suggest that specific scientific knowledge may have to be allied with social skills to launch any type of collaborative research, especially international research. Interestingly, social skills may also have some impact on the way researchers come into contact with collaborative team members. Close to 50% of the researchers surveyed indicated that they had contacted collaborators by chance at international events, such as working sessions, presentations, conferences or related events. This fact, therefore, should be taken as clear evidence to support a greater allocation of funds for the creation and support of research/scientific networks, where researchers can meet and get to know each other, opening the door to future joint research.

Although it is true that obtaining funding was not one of the main collaborative project motivations reported by researchers, we firmly believe that *funding* is an essential component for collaborative research projects, at least internationally. In the participants' experience, the most usual funding tools are project funding, institutional funding and mobility programmes. Industry funding is minimal, a circumstance that may also largely have to do with the scarce collaboration reported between industry and the university or public research organisations. It is also remarkable that close to 50% of the funding for research collaboration with EU/LAC is reported as coming from initiatives focused on general biomedical/health research, instead of specific programmes focused on PerMed. This may be indicative of a lack of specialised PerMed instruments or tools. Taking into account the numerous EU initiatives, projects and actions, the logical deduction would be that the shortage is more accentuated in the LAC environment. The supposition that funding is key is also in line with the survey responses on the main *barriers* that prevent research collaboration: The lack of opportunities to access funding clearly appears in first place with more than 50% of the responses, while inadequate funding timelines are the number-three barrier.

To find out if the particular circumstances of a researcher's environment or scientific system could negatively influence collaboration, survey participants were asked if they had collaborated with other regions in the area of health/personalised medicine research. Although almost 75% stated that they had done so, 62% reported that it was practically as easy to collaborate with countries from other regions as it was to collaborate with the EU or LAC countries, and only slightly more than 18% considered that it was more difficult to collaborate with non-EU/LAC countries. Unsurprisingly, more than 80% of non-EU/LAC collaborations were with North-American countries. This is probably due to reasons such as the prestige and reputation of many universities and research organisations in that area, especially in the USA, which is one of the world's leading research countries. These institutions are therefore a priority target for many researchers, who are willing to benefit from US collaboration.

It is interesting to note that, according to the "related research" section and, more specifically, in relation to the benefits of collaboration, survey participants indicated that "jointly authored publications" (mainly, research articles) were by far the main *outcomes* of the collaborative research process. This can be seen as logical and expected, since in many different evaluation processes, for example for the selection of research project proposals, for the recruitment of candidates for academic positions or research grants, or even for the *ex- post* evaluation of research projects or programmes, publications are one of the main items to be assessed. And in these evaluation processes, not only the number of publications is considered, but also their quality based on indicators such as the reputation of the journal in which they have been published (impact factor and quartiles), development of publications in collaboration with other institutions (especially at the international level), altmetric indicators (readings, downloads, etc.) or open access to the contents of the publications. Respondents also pointed to the acquisition of research grants and the promotion of capacity building across different research centres as another major focus of research collaboration. As with publications, the inclusion of the 'collaboration' component, especially at the international level, is essential to obtain funding and grants to attract qualified research staff and support the training of future researchers.

It also seems important to point out an issue related to the gender of the participants in the survey. Although there is not a very notable imbalance between the number of men and women who responded, the percentage of men exceeded the percentage of women by just over 20 points. Obviously, this may be a reflection of the underrepresentation of women in science and research and the imbalance that has existed until recently in matters such as women's access to research career opportunities and research career consolidation, which can also have adverse effects when it comes to access to funding and research support, positions of greater responsibility and relevance, etc. (Bellotti et al., 2022; Ceci & Williams, 2011; Ioannidis et al., 2023; O'Connor, 2019).

To conclude, in view of the growing body of scientific and academic literature on PerMed and the increasing number of PerMed research policy initiatives and actions, we can state that personalised medicine is not an emerging phenomenon. Rather, it can be considered a fixture that is being increasingly adapted and implemented in the advanced societies of regions such as the European Union, where PerMed has become a priority. Responses to a specific question in the questionnaire designed for this research reveal that more than half of the respondents consider PerMed to be a research priority in their countries. However, the large set of actions and projects implemented has outstripped the number of initiatives or studies analysing, monitoring or evaluating their advances, outputs or impacts. We strongly believe that analyses such as the one reported here can be useful for these purposes, help to better understand the reality of international scientific collaborations and support the design of collaborative programmes. Thus, although the methodology and analysis reported here focus on the field of PerMed, they might be extrapolated and applied to any other field of knowledge, where they can be expected to be of great value and become an effective tool to support the decision-making processes of practitioners and officers in charge of designing international collaborative RTD programmes in ITS ministries and funding agencies.

Particularly relevant to this last idea is previous research by authors such as Edler et al. (2012), who stated that: "In terms of methods, evaluations using survey and peer review methods are perceived to be of higher quality. This confirms that there is a general, often unquestioned, belief in survey data and expert opinion". The use of tools such as descriptive statistics for the analysis of survey results is also reported in several previous research papers. In the area of medicine, clear examples are those of Rasmussen et al. (2018), who "used only descriptive statistics" to analyse data from a survey on academia-industry collaboration in clinical trials, or Noonan et al. (2018), where the results of a specific survey to identify facilitators and barriers to international collaboration in spinal cord injury were processed and assessed.

8. Limitations

Some important limitations of this research should be borne in mind. Firstly, the survey was addressed to the corresponding authors of scientific publications who are moreover mainly employed at public research institutions. This, of course, clearly biases the results, as account is not taken of the opinions of other contributors or of researchers employed by other types of organisations, such as private companies. Furthermore, the views of other researchers whose collaborations may have led to other types of publications

(reports, presentations, etc.) or results other than publications (software, datasets, etc.) are not reflected, either. In addition, the study is very much oriented towards two specific geographical regions, so its results can only be understood in their particular context.

Secondly, the questionnaire response rate is rather moderate, so the survey results should be considered a rough approach to a better understanding of the main aspects that characterise scientific collaboration between EU and LAC researchers on the subject of PerMed. The results cannot be used to try to explain the phenomenon of research collaboration in general, nor can they be extrapolated beyond the scope, population and context defined in this study. However, this does not detract from the fact that these results are of interest for the creation of strategies and the definition of collaborative research actions in the field of PerMed.

9. Future lines of research

Further developments of this work offer new opportunities for the future research work. Firstly, the use of complementary methodologies such as case studies and interviews could be helpful to analyse the section on “facilitating aspects for the success of research collaborations” included in the theoretical framework, as that was not considered for the design of the EULAC-PerMed project survey.

Secondly, the use of additional techniques and approaches from disciplines such as bibliometrics, analyses beyond descriptive statistics or expert judgment (peer review), could be useful to carry out a validation process of the results, to perform more sophisticated analyses with more in-depth information and more accurate interpretation of the outcomes.

10. Funding

This work has been supported by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Societal Challenges – Health, demographic change and well-being grant agreement No 825173.

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Antonio J Gómez-Núñez, Antonio Perianes-Rodríguez, Erika Sela, Joaquín Guinea, *International research collaboration in personalized medicine between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean*, Research Evaluation, Volume 33, 2024, rvae046, <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvae046>

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